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Instructional Technologies and Training Models in Industry 4.0: An Explorative Literature Review

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Abstract

Context: Due to the constant development of technologies, the concept and the characteristics of the fourth industrial revolution are still being defined, because the future evolution of the phenomenon and its implications are not clear yet. Consequently, it is important for VET systems to stay up-to-date on this phenomenon so that they can keep the trainers' teaching practices and the students' curricula in line with technological evolutions. The present contribution aims at collecting and systematizing useful information to better profile the set of direct and indirect consequences of the industry 4.0 phenomenon on training processes, training methods and training contexts.

Method: The study consists of an exploratory literature review performed on 3 wide databases, following the guidelines proposed by Petticrew & Roberts, (2006) for systematic review.

Findings: According to the provisional results, a propensity to integrate continuous training models and practices in order to foster experiential learning was found in most of the contributions. Furthermore, a set of frequently used teaching methods, models and industry 4.0 technologies were identified.

Conclusion: According to the preliminary results, experiential methodologies enhanced by the use of ad-hoc technologies are at the centre of the contributions analysed. Research, both in the technological and educational spheres, thus seems to have high expectations of the potential of technological innovation to support learning processes.

Keywords

Industry 4.0, vocational education and training, continuous learning, literature review, technologies for training

1 Introduction

According to the World Economic Forum report entitled "Changes in the world of work", the ongoing transformations in the labour market due to the fourth industrial revolution will end in 2030 when this will have involved and transform every kind of new or already existing job (WEF, 2019). Regardless of the plausibility of these forecasts, it is undeniable that the growing technological innovation which characterizes this phenomenon brought substantial changes both in productive and, consequently, social contexts. Due to the constant evolution of the

technologies involved, the concept and the characteristics of the fourth industrial revolution are still being defined, because the future evolution of the phenomenon and its implications are not clear yet (Sangmeister et al., 2018; Winterton & Turner, 2019). Consequently, it is important for VET systems to stay up-to-date on the evolution of this phenomenon so that they can keep their students' curricula up-to-date. At the same time, however, it is crucial that VET trainers are also aware of the evolving teaching methodologies and learning support technologies that are emerging within Industry 4.0. So, which are the new technologies used for training purposes that are spreading, or that could spread, in industry 4.0 companies and organizations? How are the new training technologies used? Which learning models do they refer to? The present contribution aims at collecting and systematizing useful information to better profile the set of direct and indirect consequences of the industry 4.0 phenomenon on training processes, training methods and training contexts. Furthermore, the purpose of this study is to collect and systematize useful information to better profile the set of direct and indirect consequences of the Industry 4.0 phenomenon on training processes, training methods and training contexts, to make useful information available to VET stakeholders and policymakers.

2 Methodology

The explorative literature review was conducted following the methodological guidelines suggested by (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006) for the systematic review in social sciences. This stepwise process allows checking the literature according to specific criteria for searching and selecting the studies. Given the exploratory intent of the present study, these guidelines were applied to a restricted database group. 375 studies were identified by querying the databases Web of Sciences, Eric and GoogleScholar via the string 'training AND industry 4.0'. Of these, 41 passed the following selection criteria and were analysed:

- the study is explicitly contextualized in the Industry 4.0 phenomenon;
- the study proposes, tests, or describes the use of strategies, methodological frameworks, or technologies employed or to be employed for training in the context of Industry 4.0 (all contributions presenting tools that are not used for training purposes are excluded);
- the paper is written in English or Italian;
- the study was published after 2015.

Given the intention to study what training paradigms and technologies are used and for what purposes, no exclusion criteria were applied concerning journals from subject areas other than education and vocational training. The selected documents were analysed to extract the following information: type of publication, research methodology used, training context, training methodological approach adopted directly or indirectly, training technologies covered, training topic and study nationality.

3 Provisional results

By cross-referencing the selected document's metadata, it was possible to make some initial considerations. Of the $n=41$ texts analysed $n=31$ are articles, $n=8$ are part of conference proceedings and $n=2$ are book chapters. All of the contributions are in English even though the geographical areas of origin differ: more than half were produced in the European Union area ($n=25$), while the remainder in Asia ($n=1$), Colombia ($n=1$), India ($n=2$), Mexico ($n=2$), Russia ($n=5$), Saudi Arabia ($n=2$), Turkey ($n=1$), South Africa ($n=1$) and the UK ($n=1$). The studies were conducted using different research methods; specifically, $n=15$ studies using quantitative methods, $n=11$ case studies, $n=10$ theoretical contributions, $n=3$ qualitative studies and $n=2$ literature reviews. These initial elements suggest that the topic of Industry 4.0 training is also a subject of interest outside the European Union, which promotes various aspects of Industry 4.0

both through directives and through the national plans of member countries. Furthermore, the presence of case studies and theoretical articles through which prototypes of new technologies are proposed to support training and production processes could depend on Industry 4.0 technology for training is still in an experimental phase, and at least part of the technologies that characterise it is still imperfect. Another particularly interesting piece of information that emerged when analysing the metadata of the examined publications is their publishing provenance and, consequently, the audience to which they are addressed. Only n=9 of the selected n=41 studies were published in journals about the education and training sector, while the majority came from journals, books and proceedings dealing with engineering, computer science, robotics, design, economics and applied sciences. This suggests that the Industry 4.0 technologies for training are subject of interest both for the educational sector and different disciplinary fields, which are in some way representative of the respective production sectors involved in the industry 4.0 phenomenon.

The following tables synthesize what emerged from the analysis by grouping the information according to the models and methods used for training (Table 1) and the technologies used to support training (Table 2). Both tables show in the left column the main elements that emerged, while the right column shows the references of the studies where the respective elements are named.

Table 1

Training methods and models for Industry 4.0

Training methods and models	References
Simulation	Beloglazov et al., (2020) Strubelt et al., (2019) Zawadzki et al., (2020) Pérez et al., (2019)
Gamification	Tsourma et al., (2019)
Project-based learning, practical learning e-learning by doing	López et al., (2020) Salah et al., (2019) Luque-Vega et al., (2019) Sackey et al., (2020)
Training on the job	Roldán et al., (2019) Abidi et al., (2019) Kravčík et al., (2017)
Virtual factory	(Kaasinen et al., (2020)
Collaborative Learning	Koren & Klamma, (2018) Luis et al., (2019) Burritt & Christ, (2016)
Learning Factory	Abele et al., (2017) Schallock et al., (2018) Caldarola et al., (2018)
Mixed methodologies	Cantú-Ortiz et al., (2020) Chong et al., (2018) Fernández-Caramés & Fraga-Lamas, (2020) Azevedo & Almeida, (2021)
Experiential learning	De Vin et al., (2019)

Table 2
Technologies 4.0 for training

Technologies	References
Virtual and augmented reality	Abidi et al., (2019) Pérez et al., (2019) Roldán et al., (2019) Salah et al., (2019) Tsourma et al., (2019) Zawadzki et al., (2020) Schroeder et al., (2017b) Tran et al., (2019) Vidal-Balea et al., (2020) Marino et al., (2021) Tzimas et al., (2019) Longo et al., (2017)
Artificial Intelligence and Chatbot	Cantú-Ortiz et al., (2020) Casillo et al., (2021)
3D technologies	Bushmeleva et al., (2020)
Internet of Things	Koren & Klamma, (2018) Kravčík et al., (2017)
Web-based application	Moldovan, (2020) Gurjanov et al., (2021) Tsourma et al., (2019)

To answer the research questions is also useful to know the topics of training processes proposed in the contributions analysed. This information has been extracted and categorised in Table 3.

Table 3
Training topics

Category	Specific topic
Industry 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI technologies • Automation • Characteristics of industry 4.0 for VET providers • Digital competencies for industry 4,0 • Industrial cybersicurity • Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) • Industry 4.0 technologies
Operating in manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Additive manufacturing • Assembly • Complex Manufacturing Tasks • Computer Integrated Manufacturing • Manufacturing • Manufacturing assembly • manufacturing execution" • Manufacturing process • Manufacturing production stations activities • Manufacturing production stations activities • Manufacturing related areas • Processing sector industry • Production line tasks • Skills for manufacturing companies

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting factory workers
Engineering and design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The design process of biomedical products. • Development of high-order thinking processes in the engineering field • Engineering • Engineers at the workplace • Graphic engineering • Industrial engineering • Integrating Industry 4.0 into engineering teaching (in particular 3d modelling)
Transversal skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decision making • English course • Human resources management • Infrastructure that accumulates knowledge in demand by the intellectual industry • Innovative training solutions in high-tech workplace settings • Knowledge sharing • Lean Production • Management of emergencies • Organizing apprenticeship • Problem-solving • Skills enrichment in general • Work-based-learning design • Workplace learning and training on the way towards Industry 4.0
Specific technological skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Transition in Small and Medium Enterprises • Electronic and Electrical Equipment Repair • Fusion 360 software • Machine tool setup • Mechatronic • PLC programming • Robot controlling • Smart operators skills
More ...	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy resource planning • Finance • Marketing • mineral mining • Political science • Sociology

Table 3 shows the preponderance of technical subjects, especially in engineering and manufacturing, both high-profile and operator-oriented. Another category particularly present is that of transversal skills, understood in the broadest sense of the term. The manufacturing and engineering sector is, in most cases, the focus of interest in training 4.0. In this regard, Mingaleva & Vukovic, (2020) propose a methodological approach for the training of new engineers for Industry 4.0, in an attempt to establish conformity between educational products and labour market needs by providing training for specialised professionals required by specific employers.

4 Discussion and conclusion

The results of the review show that, when investigating the context of Industry 4.0, the use of technology and its characteristics also play a central role in continuous training. In particular, the category of technologies that is most often proposed and studied as support for training processes is that which includes virtual and augmented reality. These technologies, of course, are not new in the educational and training sphere, but probably, the drive of technological innovation sees in these a great deal of potential for development, as well as opportunities both concerning the efficiency of learning processes and, in turn, allowing an advantage in economic terms. Indeed, virtual reality makes it possible to greatly reduce the costs of experience-based training. These technologies are not only used to create immersive learning experiences that simulate or enrich work experiences but also to enable greater sharing of corporate know-how, as well as communication with experts inside and outside the company and then make them available in the most user-friendly way possible to learners. As already mentioned, concerning methodological approaches, what emerges is the massive presence of experiential approaches, ranging from simulation to work-based learning to blended methodologies.

In conclusion, according to the preliminary results, experiential methodologies enhanced by the use of ad-hoc technologies are at the centre of the contributions analysed. Research, both in the technological and educational spheres, thus seems to have high expectations of the potential of technological innovation to support learning processes. It is deemed necessary to further deepen the analysis of the contributions to better answer the research questions and to outline a provisional draft curriculum of competencies for VET teachers that takes into account the development of the Industry 4.0 phenomenon. It will then be possible to compare already formalised frameworks, e.g. the DigiCompEdu (Bocconi et al., 2018) or the multidisciplinary digital competencies model by Roll & Ifenthaler, (2021) with what has emerged.

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